

Supplementary Information

Tailoring PVDF membranes surface topography and hydrophobicity by a sustainable two-steps phase separation process

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Table S1. Some properties of PVDF and selected solvents [1-5]

Material	δ^a (MPa ^{1/2})	δ_d (MPa ^{1/2})	δ_p (MPa ^{1/2})	δ_h (MPa ^{1/2})	$\Delta\delta^b$ (MPa ^{1/2})	T_m^c (°C)	μ^d (Debye)	η^e @25°C (cP)	D_{w-s}^f @25°C 10 ⁶ (cm ² /s)
PVDF	23.2	17.2	12.5	9.2	-	170 to 175	-	-	-
N,N-Dimethylacetamide (DMA)	22.8	16.8	11.5	10.2	1.5	-20	2.0-3.81	0.92	
N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP)	22.9	17.9	12.3	7.2	2.1	-16 to -24	4.04-4.12	1.67	9.3
N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF)	24.8	17.4	13.7	11.3	2.5	-58	2.0-3.86	0.80	17.1
Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	27	18.85	16.4	10.2	4.3	19	3.9	2.0	6.9
Water	48.2	13.3	31.3	34.2	31.5	0	1.82-1.85	0.89	-

^a δ is the total solubility parameter calculated as: $\delta = (\delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2 + \delta_h^2)^{1/2}$

^b difference in solubility parameters with PVDF

^c melting point (T_m)

^d electric dipole moment (μ)

^e dynamic viscosity (η)

^f diffusion coefficient of water in the solvent

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